

POSTMODERN LANDMARKS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN THE DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE OPTIONAL CURRICULUM

Gabriela Anca BUNĂIAȘU ¹

Teacher, “Nicolae Balcescu” Middle School, Craiova, Romania

Abstract

The article addresses the issue of the methodology for designing, implementing and evaluating the optional curriculum, based on the orientations of the postmodern curriculum and from the perspective of curricular flexibility and the operationalization of the curricular integration model at the school level. In this sense, the two parts of the article are correlated and integrated into the issue addressed, through the unity between the scientific foundations analyzed in the first part and the presentation, in the second part, of the process and results of an investigation regarding the optional curriculum.

The first part of the article analyzes the characteristics of the postmodern curriculum and the integrated curriculum, as well as the curricular models that underlie the methodologies adopted and flexibilized at the school level, in the curricular project. Thus, curricular decentralization, the subjective dimension of educational processes, the competency-centered curricular design model, methodological models of curricular design and management are highlighted and correlated.

The second part, focused on the investigative approach, analyzes the research process through references to objectives, hypotheses, the instrument used - the opinion questionnaire, the relationships between variables, the relevance and significance of the results obtained. Also, directions for expanding the study of the issue are advanced, within the framework of further research, of an experimental nature.

Keywords : postmodern paradigm in education and curriculum; optional curriculum; modular-integrated curriculum approach; curriculum design and management at the school level; curricular strategies focused on developing students' transversal competencies.

1. Conceptual and methodological premises

During the period of postmodernism in education, in the initial stage, the educational curriculum was reevaluated, optimized, developed and operationalized in the light of axiological, conceptual and methodological specific to the subjective dimension of the educational process. Following these steps, the postmodern educational curriculum is characterized by the following attributes:

- focusing the objectives of fundamental and empirical research on *understanding the curriculum* (Pinar, 1998), which targets the perceptions, representations and ideology of the curricular domain, unlike the curricular

perspective of modernism, centered on *curriculum development*, according to Tyler 's rational-structuralist model (Bunăiașu, 2011, p. 19);

- the analysis of the curriculum as a “pedagogical construct” (Potolea, 2002), which involves the transition to a *transactional curriculum* , at the level of design and the curricular process, focused on the valorization by students in the learning process of their own processes and mechanisms for constructing knowledge scientific knowledge and understanding (Gray, 1997, Joița, 2006);

- highlighting the implications of the constructivist paradigm in the postmodern curriculum (Joița, 2006, Păun, 2002, Siebert, 2001, apud Bunăiașu, 2010, p. 15-16): giving up normative objectives, in favor of objectives with a higher degree of generality and targeting the psychic processes and own mechanisms involved in capitalizing on personal experiences and gaining new ones, in contexts of making training and learning more flexible, of interactional relationships and of the variability of training situations; analyzing didactic design and thinking about training processes from the perspective of building methodological alternatives, in the spirit of cognitivism and constructivism, which avoid excessive rationalization and templateization of the teaching act and transpose the desideratum of adaptation to the needs and interests of students, as well as to the capacities, aptitudes, styles and individual learning rhythms; valorization of holistic assessment, through which the level of achievement of high-value objectives in personal development, defined in terms of skills and highlighted through cognitive, actional , socio-relational performances, is appreciated ;

- the multidimensional approach to the educational curriculum (Potolea, 2002), through constructions that correlate curricular elements (purposes, contents, instructional and evaluation strategies), in the sense of

the general objectives of student development and according to postmodern curricular guidelines: competency-centered curriculum, student-centered curriculum, constructivist curriculum, differentiated and personalized curriculum;

- valorization of the optional curriculum, which transposes the school's curricular project within its own educational offer, which responds to the educational needs and curricular preferences of students, as well as the correlation of curricular structures in official programs, predominantly focused on the specialized field with the integrated approach.

The optional curriculum transposes these orientations of postmodern education, through structures alternative and complementary curricula to the official curriculum, being based on epistemological principles and the integrated learning model.

Thus, the design of the optional curriculum adopts, to a greater extent, the characteristics of the processual and situational models, which diversify the competency-centered curricular model. The implementation of the optional curriculum is based on constructivist instructional strategies, to a greater extent than the official one, where methodical rationalism is adopted for the broad, logically staggered contents and for directing the in-depth knowledge of the school subject.

Based on these premises and personal methodological experiences, I considered it appropriate and necessary to conduct a micro-research, such as an impact study, through which we would reveal concepts, opinions and educational practices in the optional curriculum and highlight possibilities for optimization and curricular development.

The basic assumption of the research is:

If optional curricular programs are designed, implemented and developed in the spirit of the methodological principles of the postmodern curriculum and integrated learning, then they will generate alternative curricular paths to the official curriculum and will facilitate, to a greater extent, the development of students' transversal skills.

2. The research process

2.1. Objectives

The objectives of the study are:

1. Studying the opinions, conceptions and methodological experiences of subjects in the field of optional curriculum.
2. Systematization of curricular models and strategies, which favors the optimization and development of the optional curriculum.

2.2 . Research hypotheses

2.2.1. The adoption of curricular design and management models at the optional curriculum level, specific to the postmodern curriculum, generates alternative curricular programs to the official curriculum, with a greater degree of curricular flexibility.

2.2.2. The integrated approach to the optional curriculum facilitates the development of curricular structures focused, to a greater extent, on the personal development of students.

2.3. Participants

The batch of 90 subjects, selected through the mixed sampling technique, has the following structure: 40 teachers from pre-university education, of various specialties, who have designed and implemented optional curricular programs; decision-makers from pre-university education - 15 subjects; trainers and experts - 15 subjects; students - 20 subjects.

2.4. Instrument

The main instrument used in the research was the opinion questionnaire, applied to teachers, trainers and education experts. The questionnaire consists of 20 items, which address the specific variables of the issue, the relationship of which verifies the specific hypotheses of the research. Thus, the following themes of the opinion questionnaire resulted:

1. curriculum design and management models appropriate to the optional curriculum (items 5-9);
2. the role of the integrated optional curriculum in the personal development of students (items 10-14);
3. instructional strategies specific to the optional curriculum, which facilitate the achievement of the objectives (items 15-18);
4. directions and ways to develop the optional curriculum (items 19-20).

To detail the responses, two focus group sessions were organized: a session with the: teachers, educational managers, decision-makers, experts and trainers, and another session was held with students. In the first focus group activity, the methodological choices of the subjects were analyzed in particular; the second session focused on the analysis of the educational needs and curricular preferences of the students.

3. Results

The systematization of the subjects' responses reveals opinions, conceptions and methodological options of the subjects, grouped by categories of variables for which they expressed their adherence by indicating the corresponding criteria within the items. In this manner of systematizing the responses, we obtained the following results:

Theme/Variable	Teaching staff	Experts/trainers	School managers
1. The comprehensive curriculum approach model (Potolea, 2002)	77.50%	80%	73.33%
1.1. Competency-centered curriculum design model	85%	86.66%	80%
1.2. Rational models of curriculum design	52.50%	46.66%	53.33%
1.3. Situational and process models of curriculum design	72.50%	73.33%	66.66%
2.1. The impact of the integrated optional curriculum on the development of students' transversal competences (social and civic competences, intercultural competences, capacities for synthesis and understanding of complexity, critical thinking)	82.50%	80%	73.33%
2.2. The impact of the optional curriculum in the development of students' metacognitive skills	47.50%	73.33%	66.66%
3.1. Constructivist instructional strategies	72.50%	80%	73.33%
3.2. Interactive strategies	82.50%	86.66%	80%
3.3. Strategies based on new educational technologies in virtual learning environments	57.50%	73.33%	73.33%
4.1. Training programs and courses on curriculum development issues	82.50%	86.66%	80%

We found significant differences between the responses of the subject categories only at the level of two variables, which invoke metacognitive strategies and strategies specific to virtual learning environments – which trainers, experts and school managers appreciate to a greater extent than teachers.

4. Conclusions

The results of the micro-research confirm, first of all, the increased impact of the optional curriculum on the personal development of students and in the field of curricular development, by adopting the curricular integration model. The methodological approaches valued by the subjects are part of the epistemological and methodological orientations of the postmodern curriculum, regarding the conceptualization, design and management of the curriculum.

We equally appreciate the awareness by the subjects of the need for professional development in the field of curricular development, as well as the proposal of metacognitive programs and strategies in this regard. The results of the micro-research will form the basis for the design of an experimental research, through which we intend to build and validate an optional curricular program focused on interdisciplinary relationships in the field of exact sciences, which will capitalize on elements of the curricular models invoked and valued by the subjects.

References

- Bunăiașu, C.M. (2011). *Proiectarea și managementul curriculumului la nivelul organizației școlare*. București: Editura Universitară
- Bunăiașu, C.M.(2010). *Seminarul didactic universitar*. Craiova: Universitaria.
- Joița, E. (2006). *Instruirea constructivistă – o alternativă*. București: Aramis.
- Gray,A. (1997). *Constructivist Teaching and Learning, SSTA Research Centre Report*
#97-07. <http://sakschoolboards.ca/research/instruction/97-07.htm>

- Pinar, W.F. (ed). (1998). *Curriculum Toward New Identities*. New York, Londra: Garland Publishing.
- Potolea, D. (2002). Conceptualizarea curriculum-ului. O abordare multidimensională. In Păun, E. & Potolea, D. (coord.). *Pedagogie. Fundamentări teoretice și demersuri aplicative*. Iași: Polirom.